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Opinion on the safety assessment of the absorber pads

Moisture absorbers, which include absorber pads are designed to absorb juices from the packaging of fresh or frozen meat, poultry, and seafood as well as fresh fruits and vegetables.

Absorbent pads are produced mostly from the laminate, which consists of plastic grid and "pillow" filled with absorber:

- crosslinked sodium polyacrylate, or a combination with natural cellulose
- crosslinked copolymer of sodium acrylate and methyl acrylate and 2-hydroxypropyl methacrylate or a combination with natural cellulose.

The polymer is mostly used in the form of fibers (length 6 mm, diameter 0.025 mm) connected with nonwoven fabric or cellulose in the production process, which is designed to prevent leakage of the active substance into food. Nonwoven manufacturing techniques such as pressing or calendering should prevent the movement of the polymer fibers into food.

Absorbent pads as active and intelligent materials should be in line with:

1. Regulation (EC) No 1935/2004 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 October 2004 on materials and articles intended to come into contact with food
2. Commission regulation (EC) No 450/2009 of 29 May 2009 on active and intelligent materials and articles intended to come into contact with food
3. Commission regulation (EC) No 2023/2006 of 22 December 2006 on good manufacturing practice for materials and articles intended to come into contact with food.

European Food Safety Authority (EFSA) has published below opinions on the safety assessment of liquid absorbers used in the packaging of fresh or frozen meat, poultry, fish as well as fruits and vegetables:

1. EFSA CEF Panel (EFSA Panel on Food Contact Materials, Enzymes, Flavourings and Processing Aids), 2014. Scientific Opinion on safety assessment of the

active substance, polyacrylic acid, sodium salt crosslinked, for use in active food contact materials. EFSA Journal 2014;12(7):3786

2. EFSA CEF Panel (EFSA Panel on Food Contact Materials, Enzymes, Flavourings and Processing Aids), 2014. Scientific Opinion on safety assessment of the active substance, polyacrylic acid, sodium salt, crosslinked, for use in active food contact materials. EFSA Journal 2014;12(5):3648

3. EFSA CEF Panel (EFSA Panel on Food Contact Materials, Enzymes, Flavourings and Processing Aids), 2013. Scientific Opinion on the safety evaluation of the active substance, polyacrylic acid, sodium salt, crosslinked, for use in active food contact materials. EFSA Journal 2013;11(2):3096

4. EFSA CEF Panel (EFSA Panel on Food Contact Materials, Enzymes, Flavourings and Processing Aids), 2013 Scientific Opinion on the safety evaluation of the active substance, acrylic acid, sodium salt, co-polymer with acrylic acid, methyl ester, methacrylic acid, 2-hydroxypropylester, and acrylic acid cross-linked for use in active food contact materials. EFSA Journal 2013;11(4):3154.

EFSA Panel concluded that the use of the absorbent pads containing crosslinked sodium polyacrylates or copolymers of sodium polyacrylates do not raise a safety concern when:

- are used only under conditions in which the liquid absorption capacity is not exceeded
- direct contact between the substance and the food is excluded.

Provided that the absorber pads meet the above criteria and are applied in line with their intended use and the manufacturer's instructions do not raise a risk to consumer's health.

It should be noted that, if the capacity of the absorbent pad is exceeded, it may cause delamination of the absorber and a nonwoven fabric, which is connected to the absorber, and cause the possible contact with food.

Closing of the side edges of absorber pads is one of the solutions to prevent the contact of the absorber with food, however, the use of pads with open side edges in accordance with the recommendations is safe for the consumer's health.

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